

PHTHALOCYANINE RESINS - NEW MATRIX MATERIALS FOR ADVANCED COMPOSITES

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Thermomechanical analysis was carried out for various phthalocyanine resins. The polymer based on the C-10 diamide resin was then chosen for evaluation as a potential composite matrix material in advanced aircraft. Prepregs with Thornel 300 graphite reinforcements were successfully prepared using a hot-melt technique. The processability of this material was studied by employing instrumental techniques including differential scanning calorimetry, thermal gravimetric analysis and dynamic dielectric analysis. A cure cycle was developed for the fabrication of angle-ply laminate using the conventional vacuum-bag technique in a hydraulic press. Laminate mechanical properties both in tension and in flexure were determined. The results for the C-10/T-300 samples were shown to be similar to those of an epoxy/graphite and a polyimide/graphite composite system.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composite materials have in recent years received considerable attention for potential aerospace and advanced ship applications. One example is the increasing use of these materials in the structural design of advanced conventional and V/STOL (vertical and short take-off and landing) aircraft. In this case, it is anticipated that, by incorporating the superior properties of fiber-reinforced composites, substantial weight saving may be achieved and the range and payload of the aircraft increased. But, for such applications in advanced aircraft, currently available matrix resin systems suffer many shortcomings, including moisture pick-up, thermal instability, chemical degradation, and poor storage stability in the uncured condition. Furthermore, these materials only have a maximum use temperature around 135°C. New resins are therefore being sought that will meet operational requirements at temperatures in excess of 200°C, and offer low moisture sensitivity, easy handling and superior processability.

Research efforts [1] at the Naval Research Laboratory have recently led to the development of a new class of resins called polyphthalocyanines that promise to provide the desired properties for advanced composite application. Thermomechanical properties of these resins have been studied, and the polymer based on the C-10 diamide resin in particular has been evaluated for potential application as a composite matrix material. In this report, the development of processing parameters and fabrication procedures for this material will be discussed.

RESIN CHEMISTRY

The chemistry of phthalocyanine resin synthesis and polymerization has been reported previously by Walton, Griffith and O'Rear [1]. Briefly, the reaction of 4-aminophthalonitrile with aliphatic diacid chlorides forms resin monomers having a diamide structure:

Abbreviated names are used to identify these compounds. For example, if $n = 8$ the compound is called C-10 diamide because it was made from a diacid chloride containing ten carbon atoms. Polymerization is activated by simply heating the diamide at temperatures above its melting temperature. The "B" stage and post-cure at about 200°C lead to the development of stable phthalocyanine nuclei linked through aliphatic diamide linkages. Figure 1 shows schematically the proposed phthalocyanine network structure. The figure suggests a two-dimensional network, but the more likely case is a three-dimensional structure produced by numerous out-of-plane reactions of the phthalonitrile end groups. These materials have been shown to be thermally stable [2,3] up to 260°C and their cure behavior was also examined via the torsion braid analysis of Gillham [4].

THERMOMECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The dynamic mechanical properties of four phthalocyanine polymers, each with different aliphatic chains, were studied. These polymers were based on the C-6, C-10, C-22 and C-36 diamide resins, which were cured in an air-circulating oven at 220°C for one day (one exception was for the C-36 diamide resin which required a 3-day cure). Dynamic shear modulus and polymer loss factor were determined by using a freely oscillating torsion pendulum [5] operating at ca. 1 Hz. The experiments were carried out in a nitrogen atmosphere in accordance with the recommended ASTM procedure D-2236-70. For a complete temperature scan, the sample was heated from -200°C to its glass-to-rubber transition temperature T_g at a heating rate of 1°C/min. As T_g was approached, the sample softened and the experiment had to be terminated. Therefore the glass transition temperature was estimated as the temperature where the dynamic shear modulus decreased rapidly with increasing temperature.

Fig. 1: Phthalocyanine polymerization reaction.

Figure 2 shows the variation of the glass transition temperature and the room temperature shear modulus as a function of the interaromatic aliphatic chain length. As the length of the interaromatic chain linkage is increased from six carbon atoms (C-6) to 36 carbon atoms (C-36), the polymer network becomes more flexible. One

Fig. 2: Glass transition temperature and room temperature shear modulus as a function of aliphatic chain length in number of carbon units.

therefore observes in Fig. 2 a progressive decrease in the shear modulus with increasing aliphatic chain. The high moduli of these polymers, of the order of 1 GN/m², remain fairly constant over the complete range of the analysis, except when the glass transition temperature is approached. This temperature, which determines the use temperature of the material, also decrease with increasing aliphatic chain length, ranging from 90°C for the C-36 phthalocyanine to 350°C for the C-6 polymer. Since a resin is sought to meet operational requirements at temperatures in excess of 200°C, one is limited to resins with interaromatic chain

length of no more than 14 carbon atoms. The C-10 diamide resin was therefore selected for study as a composite matrix resin based on modulus and glass transition temperature, as well as on considerations of cure versatility and material cost.

C-10/T-300 PREPREG

The C-10 diamide resin has a melting temperature of 185-192°C. Brief "B" staging of this material gives a liquid intermediate state that could be utilized for fiber-impregnation. Depending on the "B" staging temperature and the dwell time, the degree of crosslinking varies and different mixtures of compounds or oligomers are formed. The resin melting temperature at the same time is greatly reduced. Figure 3 shows the melting temperature variation of the C-10 resin heated

Fig. 3: Reduced melting temperature of C-10 resins after "B" staging at 220°C.

at 220°C for different periods of time. Resin melting temperature was measured by using a conventional Fisher-Johns melting point apparatus. It can be seen that by heating the raw resin at 220°C for only 10 minutes the melting temperature was already reduced to 93°C. As the dwell time increased, short polymer fragments began to form. This slightly increased the melting point, which approached a final level of ca. 110°C after reaching a minimum of 85°C. At this minimum point, the material remained sufficiently fluid for proper prepregging. Further heating would increase the melt viscosity beyond the point at which fiber impregnation was possible.

Thornel 300 graphite fibers (T-300, Union Carbide Company) with UC-309 finish were used as reinforcements for the production of 30.5 cm wide unidirectional prepreg tapes. Prepregging of the C-10/T-300 system was developed by using the conventional hot-melt method [6]. The resin content of the final product was ca. 32% with less than 1% residual volatiles. The prepreg, shipped in rolls, had a generally dry and brittle appearance. Sufficient tack, however, could be developed by briefly heating the material at 110°C.

THERMAL ANALYSIS

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis was carried out for the C-10/T-300 prepreg by using a Perkin-Elmer DSC-2 system. The scanning was performed over the temperature range of 310°K (37°C) to 500°K (227°C) at a heating rate of 10°K/min under a dry nitrogen atmosphere. Thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA) was also carried out by using a DuPont 900 series unit. Samples (~20 mg) were analyzed

over the temperature range of 20°C to 350°C by monitoring sample weight loss as a function of temperature. The sample was heated at a rate of 5°C/min and was continuously purged with dry nitrogen at a flow rate of 100 ml/min.

Figure 4 shows the result of a typical DSC scan for the C-10/T-300 prepreg. When compared with the reference baseline, the trace shows a multiple of endotherm

Fig. 4: DSC result for the C-10/T-300 prepreg.

peaks at 144°C, 156°C, 168°C and 190°C, respectively. The appearance of those peaks is believed to be related to the melting of resin oligomers of separate entities. A similar multiple-melting behavior was also observed in the torsion braid analysis of the C-10 resin [4]. The DSC result for the prepreps is in great contrast to that of the pure, uncured C-10 resin. In the latter case, a single melting peak appeared at 186°C and an exotherm at ca. 197°C for the onset of cure, which extended continuously into higher temperature region. The DSC record in Fig. 4 does not show any exotherm, implying that for practical purposes the cure of C-10/T-300 prepreps should be carried out at temperatures higher than 230°C (~500°K). However, TGA study of the prepreps indicated rapid weight loss taking place at temperatures higher than 275°C, (see Fig. 5). Previous study [2]

Fig. 5: Prepreg sample weight loss as a function of temperature.

also demonstrated that the cured C-10 phthalocyanine polymer was stable for extended usage up to 245°C and for short-term exposure at 260°C. These results therefore suggest that the initial cure temperature for the C-10/T-300 prepreps needs to be limited to no more than 260°C.

ISOTHERMAL CURE AND GELATION

Isothermal cure analysis was carried out at various cure temperatures in order to understand the gelation process of the matrix resin. A dynamic dielectric technique [7] was employed to monitor the curing of prepreg samples by continuously measuring the capacitance and dielectric dissipation factor ($\tan \delta_e$) as a function of cure time and temperature. The capacitance is directly proportional to the real part of sample complex dielectric permittivity, k' , whereas $\tan \delta_e$ is the ratio of the imaginary to the real part of k^* . This technique is analogous to a dynamic mechanical analysis in that the capacitance corresponds to the mechanical storage compliance and $\tan \delta_e$ to the mechanical loss tangent [8]. Therefore, the dynamic dielectric analysis (DDA) results can be related to chemo-rheological changes during the curing of a thermosetting system.

An Audrey III Dielectric Analyzer (Tetrahedron, Inc.) was used for the dynamic dielectric analysis. Figure 6 gives the schematics of this apparatus.

Fig. 6: Schematic diagram of the dynamic dielectric analyzer.

Single-ply samples, 6.35 cm in diameter, were covered with Kapton insulating films (DuPont Company) and placed in the test cell of a Di/An 300 mini-press. The cell was then closed with a pressure of ca. 0.35 MN/m² (50 psi) and sample temperature brought to the cure temperature by using the temperature controller. Electric excitation was provided by the Audrey oscillator to the sample at a fixed frequency of 10³ Hz. Sample dielectric dissipation factor ($\tan \delta_e$) was continuously monitored as a function of dwell time under isothermal curing and recorded on a strip-chart recorder.

Figure 7 shows the DDA result of the isothermal cure study for a single-ply prepreg sample. The time scale, increasing from right to left, is one hour for each large (one-inch) division. As the sample temperature was rapidly increased to the isothermal cure temperature, a small $\tan \delta_e$ peak first appeared at ca. 100°C, indicating the release of moisture. When the temperature exceeded 200°C, the material quickly melted and polymerization of phthalocyanine was also activated thermally. This resulted in a rapid increase of the dielectric dissipation until a maximum was reached, which was believed to be the gelation point [9]. The time to gelation was determined at various cure temperatures, and was plotted as a function of the inverse of temperature in Fig. 8. The result indicated that the gelation process followed an Arrhenius relationship with an activation energy of 14.95 kcal/mole, a value similar to that for the epoxies [10]. This suggests that the processability of C-10 phthalocyanine is similar to that of the epoxies.

Fig. 7: Dynamic dielectric result of the C-10/T-300 prepreg under an isothermal cure.

Fig. 8: Arrhenius plot of gel time vs. the inverse of cure temperature for the C-10/T-300 prepreg.

MONITORING THE PRESS CURE

The DDA technique may also be applied to perform *in situ* monitoring of the cure of large composite samples in a hydraulic press. Angle-ply laminates, 25.4 cm x 25.4 cm, were laid up by hand between two aluminum foil electrodes with a glass fabric dam around the sample. The complete lay-up was then placed in a Kapton vacuum bag for press cure. Connections were made from the foil electrodes to the Audrey III system, which measured both the sample capacitance and dissipation factor as a function of cure time and temperature at a fixed frequency of 10^3 Hz.

Fig. 9 shows the DDA result when this technique was applied *in situ* to the fabrication of a 16-ply laminate sample in a press. The sample, subjected to the

Fig.9: Dielectric dissipation of laminate samples during a press cure.

cure cycle of Fig. 9C, was cured at 260°C . When sample temperature was rapidly raised to this cure temperature, the dissipation curve showed initially a broad melting peak (Fig. 9A), followed by a rapid increase in $\tan \delta_{\text{C}}$ to reach the gel point. This information was used to determine the desired time for the application of press pressure in order to fabricate laminates with very low void contents. The sample was then cured under pressure until the heat was cut off. The press was slowly cooled to room temperature and then opened for the removal of the laminate sample.

The C-10/T-300 prepregs produced had only ca. 32% resin content. An attempt to increase laminate resin content was made by adding resin powder to the sample. Initially, a pre-measured amount of raw resin was distributed uniformly by sprinkling it between plies as part of the hand lay-up procedure. However, during heating an excessive amount of resin flow accompanied the melting; this excess could not be contained by the glass fabric dam. The corresponding dissipation record in Fig. 9B showed a very pronounced melting peak in this case. Proper control of this excessive resin flow is necessary. Samples of raw resin were therefore briefly "B" staged in an oven preheated to 195°C for different periods of time, and DSC scans performed on each sample. Fig. 10 shows the DSC records for these samples performed at a heating rate of $10^{\circ}\text{K}/\text{min}$ from 310°K (37°C) to 500°K (227°C). It can be seen that initially the resin had a single melting peak centered around 189°C (462°K). As the sample was heated for over 10 minutes at 195°C , multiple

Fig. 10: DSC record of "B" staged C-10 phthalocyanine resins.

melting peaks began to appear. Broad exotherms were also observed, indicating the presence of a meta-stable crystallized phase formed as the sample was removed from the oven and rapidly "quenched" at room temperature. If the cooling rate was reduced, and repeated DSC scans were taken, those exotherms would disappear. As the dwelling time at 195°C was increased to 55 minutes, the melting temperature was suppressed to ca. 57°C (330°K) with an additional, very weak endotherm at 177°C (450°K). From Fig. 8 it may be estimated that at 195°C the gelation time is over 4-1/2 hours. So, even after 55 minutes, the percent of gel is negligible, but a suppression of the melting temperature to as low as ca. 60°C could be very significant for future prepregging of this material. The DSC record of the 20-min. sample compared favorably with that of the C-10/T-300 prepreg. Therefore by heating the raw resin to be added to a laminate at 195°C for 20 minutes, one can be assured that the added resin has thermal characteristics similar to those in the prepregs. During the press cure, the dynamic dielectric record of Fig. 9A was subsequently restored. With this technique, laminate resin contents were successfully controlled over the range of 32-40%.

POST-CURE STUDY

In order to optimize laminate mechanical properties, a proper post-cure for the composite sample is required. Based on the thermal stability data for the C-10 resin [2], it was decided that the post-cure temperature should not exceed 245°C. Unidirectional 16-ply composite laminates were therefore fabricated and specimens cut from the laminate for mechanical testing. The short beam shear test (ASTM-D2344) was chosen to determine the interlaminar shear strength, a resin-dominated property. The flexure test (ASTM-D790) was selected to measure the laminate flexural strength and modulus, which are fiber-dominated properties. Before testing, specimens were post-cured at 245°C for various lengths of time. Fig. 11 shows the measured mechanical properties as a function of the post-cure time. It is clear that all

Fig. 11: Effect of post-cure time on laminate mechanical properties.

three properties, the flexural strength and modulus and the shear strength showed optimum values when the sample was post-cured at 245°C for 72 hours. Results of an earlier thermal aging study [3] on the fracture energy of neat C-10 resins also showed that C-10 phthalocyanine exhibited maximum toughness when aged at 240°C for ca. 72 hours. As the post-cure time exceeded 72 hours, the mechanical properties seemed to level off, indicating that the C-10/T-300 system is more than

adequate for 200-230°C (400-450°F) applications. For practical purposes, laminates perhaps should be post-cured up to ca. 65 hours so that the maximum strength and modulus may be obtained in the field as the composite components continue to be exposed to the thermal flux from the environment. However, for laboratory evaluation all laminates were post-cured at 245°C for 72 hours in order to obtain optimized mechanical properties.

LAMINATE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Sixteen-ply angle plies and 16-ply quasi-isotropic laminates were prepared. Because the amount of prepreg material was limited, the angle plies consisted of

Fig. 12: Stacking sequences of angle-ply and quasi-isotropic laminates.

only two orientations: $+15^\circ$ and $+45^\circ$. The quasi-isotropic laminates had the configuration of $(90^\circ, +45^\circ, 0^\circ)$. The stacking sequence is schematically shown in Fig. 12. The mechanical response of the laminates was evaluated by performing tensile tests with specimens 10 cm x 1.25 cm x 0.2 cm in size. The specimens were machined in such a way that the loading direction bisected the included angle between fiber orientations. All tests were carried out in an INSTRON with the cross-head moving at a speed of 0.125 cm/min. A three-point flexural test was also performed in accordance with ASTM-D790. The data are listed together with the tensile properties for comparison.

All test results are given in Table 1, where the data for the Narmco 5208/T-300 epoxy/graphite and Hexcel F178/T-300 (polyimide/graphite) composites obtained earlier are also included [11, 12]. It can be seen that the C-10/T-300 system exhibited tensile and flexural moduli similar to the F178/T-300 material. In all cases, the 5208/T-300 composite showed higher strength than F178/T-300 and C-10/T-300 samples, particularly when the fiber orientation was $2\theta = 30^\circ$. The tensile properties of angle-ply laminates have a strong dependence on fiber orientation. For small θ , the tensile properties is dominated by the fiber strength. As the included angle increases, the role of the matrix becomes increasingly important in its contribution to the distribution of the load. In those cases, the data clearly showed that the three composite systems were similar. For the popular quasi-isotropic design of laminates, the C-10/T-300 composite exhibited good strength properties, with even higher tensile modulus than the other two systems. The fracture behavior of the C-10/T-300 laminates under complex in-plane loading has also been studied recently at this Laboratory [13]. The onset of crack propagation under various combinations of in-plane loading conditions was determined both at room temperature and at 232°C (450°F). The results again showed that the C-10/T-300 composites exhibited a similar performance in both cases to the

Table 1: Mechanical Properties of angle-ply laminates

Orientation	Property (GPa)	5208/T300	F178/T300	C10/T300
Quasi-isotropic	Strength: tensile	0.48	0.39	0.47
		flexural	-	0.52
	Modulus: tensile	48.3	62.8	75.2
		flexural	-	37.3
2 θ =30 $^{\circ}$	Strength: tensile	0.75	0.61	0.56
		flexural	1.03	0.81
	Modulus: tensile	104.9	97.3	93.2
		flexural	107.0	91.1
2 θ =90 $^{\circ}$	Strength: tensile	0.16	0.13	0.11
		flexural	-	0.28
	Modulus: tensile	26.9	40.7	37.3
		flexural	-	17.3
2 θ =150 $^{\circ}$	Strength: tensile	0.041	0.035	0.031
	Modulus: tensile	10.4	26.2	22.8

epoxy and polyimide systems. Physical characterization of the laminates showed that all laminate thicknesses were ca. 0.0125-0.014 cm/ply. The resin contents ranged from ca. 30% for the 5208/T-300 laminates to ca. 38% for the C-10/T-300 and the F-178/T-300 laminates.

CONCLUSION

The C-10 phthalocyanine resin has been demonstrated to be a potential matrix material for advanced composites. This polymer exhibited long-term stability at temperatures up to 245 $^{\circ}$ C [2], and its moisture uptake is less than that in epoxies or polyimides [14]. The phthalocyanine reaction can be induced to proceed under less severe thermal and catalytic conditions than those required for the acetylene reaction. The resin monomer represents a chemically simple and pure system for easy quality control when compared with the complex formulations of other systems such as epoxies [15]. The resin monomers and prepolymers are also virtually inert at room temperature so that no cold storage is required. Upon melting, the resin flows readily and successful prepregging has been demonstrated by using the conventional hot-melt technique. Instrumental techniques including DSC, TGA and DDA were used to identify necessary processing parameters for the development of fabrication procedures for this new resin. The processability of C-10 phthalocyanine was shown to be comparable to that of conventional epoxies. The combined application of DSC data and *in situ* DDA during a press cure proved to be a useful technique for controlling laminate resin contents. Mechanical properties have been determined in both tensile and flexural tests for the C-10/T-300 system, and these results were compared with those of the 5208/T-300 and the F-178/T-300 composites. It was found that the C-10/T-300 samples exhibited similar properties as the samples from the other two systems. With the quasi-isotropic design for the laminates, the C-10/T-300 samples even showed better properties than the others.

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